

ТАЛАБАЛАРНИНГ ИЖОДКОРЛИК ҚОБИЛИЯТЛАРИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ МУАММОСИ

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Аннотация. Ушбу мақолада шахсинг ижодкорлик қобилиятлари тўғрисидаги назарий билимлар таҳлил қилинган, шунингдек шахс ижодкорлик қобилиятини ўрганиш устида олиб борилган амалий тадқиқотлар кўриб чиқилиб, уларни тизимли ўрганиш асосида таклиф ва хулосалар баён этилган.

Калит сўзлар: ижодкорлик қобилиятлари, кадриятлар, эҳтиёжлар, идеаллар, дунёқараш, кашфиётлар, хотира, эътибор, мулоҳаза юритиш, пси-хик реакция тезлиги, интеллектуал иқтидор, креативлик, синтетик ёндошув.

ТВОРЧЕСКИЕ НАВЫКИ СТУДЕНТОВ ПРОБЛЕМА РАЗВИТИЯ

Аннотация. В статье анализируются теоретические знания о творческих способностях человека, а также рассматриваются практические исследования, проведенные по изучению творческих способностей человека, и представлены их рекомендации и выводы, основанные на систематическом исследовании.

Ключевые слова: творческие способности, ценности, потребности, идеалы, мировоззрение, открытия, память, внимание, рассуждение, скорость мыслительной реакции, интеллектуальные способности, креативность, синтетический подход.

CREATIVE SKILLS OF STUDENTS PROBLEM OF DEVELOPMENT.

Annotation. The article analyzes theoretical knowledge about human creativity, and also considers practical research conducted to study human creativity, and presents their recommendations and conclusions based on systematic research.

Key words: creativity, values, needs, ideals, worldview, discoveries, memory, attention, reasoning, speed of mental reaction, intellectual abilities, creativity, synthetic approach

Pedagogical theory and practice are actively developing methods aimed at finding factors related to the creative activity of students and aimed at developing creative abilities.

A synthetic approach seems to solve all the problems of creativity. In fact, creative achievements are influenced by the characteristics of mental processes, personality traits, and motivation. However, it is accepted in the psychology literature not to confuse motivation, character, and abilities. Defining the concept of creativity, the researchers went from the specific problems of creative abilities to the general problem of the creative person. In this case, there is a need to distinguish the priority specific aspects of the structural elements that determine the creativity of a person.

Based on the analysis of the proposed approaches, as well as pedagogical work experience, we distinguished the following characteristics: character (confidence in one's own strength; independence; clarity of mind; new and accepting something extraordinary; to treat unknown and unsolved situations with high tolerance, to be constructively active in these situations; reflexive point of view), abilities (seeing problems, readiness of memory, application of knowledge to new situations, easy adaptation and imagination, dialectic and originality of thinking, foreseeing the result, critical thinking), will (ability of self-control, striving to overcome difficulties, conveying ideas to the end), feelings (desire to know, surprise, inspiration). Undoubtedly, the orientation of a person serves as a trigger for the manifestation of the mentioned set of unique characteristics of a creative person: his interest in the chosen activity, his desire to know, his desire to involve himself in work.

Heuristic methods of solving creative problems were studied by Yu.N. Kulyutkin. By heuristics, he understands certain procedures that lead to correct solutions and conclusions with a certain degree of probability, in contrast to algorithms that guarantee a successful solution... heuristic methods and methods are described as procedures that reduce the number of options on the way to a solution.

In the 30s of the 20th century, A.P. Nechaev studied technical creativity. He studied a number of abilities and qualities of a person (memory, attention, reasoning, speed of mental reaction, imagination, interests, typical characteristics of a person) using tests. Based on the observations, the scientist comes to the conclusion that the general questions that underlie technical inventions are similar to the general questions that give rise to artistic and scientific creativity.

We see that the concept of creativity is characterized by its extraordinary versatility. There are different definitions, some of which we have looked at. There have been attempts to classify them. E.P. Torrance divided definitions of concepts into 5 groups. A.Z. Rakhimov singled out 125 main meaningful compounds reflecting the essence of creativity, which were further divided into four thematic groups. I.A. Sharshov completed the classification up to 10 groups.

Creative skills are not enough. Intellectual talent appears as a necessary, but not sufficient, condition for creative activity. Motivation, values, personality traits play a key role in the determination of creative behavior

According to a survey conducted by the Gallup Institute in America (from among 1,500 famous people randomly selected from the magazine "Who Lives in America"), the general qualities of successful creative people are distinguished: healthy thinking; knowledge of his work; believe in one's own strength; high level of general development; the ability to get things done.

There are other qualities: adaptability, independence (FRG), originality, agility of thinking (USA); self-discipline, originality, desire to stand on one's feet (France).

However, even the considered approach could not solve the problem of the creative process. There was a need to highlight a unique creative ability.

Creativity is an independent factor independent of intelligence (D.Gilford, K.Taylor). This term "creativity" appeared in Anglo-American psychology in the 60s to define the abilities of an individual reflecting the property of creating new concepts and forming new skills. E. Torrens added the ability to resist stereotyped solutions. By creativity, it refers to deficiencies in knowledge, critical thinking skills, etc.

N. Yu. Postaluk systematizes the ability of creativity, which is often distinguished by various researchers⁵:

1. The ability to see the problem. In most tests, this ability is key to creativity.
2. Originality of thinking.
3. Dialectical thinking.
4. Easy to combine and imagine.
5. Thinking dexterity.
6. Anticonformism of thinking.
7. Ability to easily come up with and develop ideas.
8. Creativity of thinking (to incoming information and to oneself).
9. The ability to evaluate and choose. 10. Transferability.

11. Readiness of memory (providing a collection of knowledge of the necessary volume and quality: systematicity, dynamism, level of generalization)

Despite the opinions of Russian scientists on the third approach to the classification of creative abilities, most Russian psychologists can be said to belong to this direction, which combines the cognitive abilities and personality characteristics of people with developed creative phenomena (D.B. Bogoyavlenskaya, V.N. Kozlenko, A.N. Luk , A.M.Matyushkin, Ya.A.Ponamarev and others).

Summarizing foreign research on the concept of creative abilities, the following can be noted:

1. Absence of a single concept

2. The presence of a rational root in each approach:

In the description of creativity, specific aspects of the perceptual field involved in thinking, imaginative operations, and creative activities are distinguished.

The specified features allow the realization of the hobby of the individual's interest in knowledge.

Let's look at the capabilities in more detail. Abilities clarify the general concept of the psyche as a property of the brain to reflect the objective world, classify this property into concrete mental functions, introduce a measure of individual expressiveness into it, give it the characteristic of practicality, and take its place in the structural structure of the psyche.

In our opinion, the psychological concept of creativity has the right to exist independently, because:

1-creative abilities are mainly related to human activity in the form of activity - creativity, in other types of activity one's own abilities are distinguished;

2- distinguishing certain abilities can be the basis for their development for one purpose.

In our opinion, the phrase creative abilities is defined by the closest type to the given concept and in the form of creative ability.

In the extended version: creative abilities are an individual property of the psychological functional system that determines the effectiveness of its creative process.

In this case, creative abilities should be included among general abilities, because they can be manifested in voluntary professional activities, and serve as a basis for special abilities along with intelligence. "All the special abilities of a person are ultimately different manifestations of his general ability to assimilate human culture and its further development.

The manifestation of creativity can be different, for example, in art and science. This should lead to a difference in creativity mechanisms. However, the reality is that some of the creative treatments are consistent, as well as revealing the creative process. Any creative process is related to setting and solving a problem. In one type of creativity (art) it is less, in others (science) it is expressed in a clearly given form. That is why our main focus will be on working with problems. As stages of the creative process, we define the problem; understand the problem; We will look at the creation of ideas for solving the problem, the composition of ideas.

In the real creative process, creative abilities are manifested in an integrated form, but the most important abilities can be distinguished at individual stages. This can serve as a basis for dividing creative abilities into structural structures, which is very important for their diagnosis and development. At the modern stage of the development of our society, there is an increasing need for creative individuals who

are able to develop unconventional solutions in problematic situations, to improvise (do without preparation). This is happening as a result of rapid development of science and technology, rapid growth of information flow, fundamental changes in politics, economy, and moral standards of the country. Based on these, the problem of the individual's creative abilities is becoming more and more urgent.

Before starting to study the creative abilities of a person, it is necessary to define the basic concepts: person, abilities, creativity. All these concepts do not have the same interpretation, which requires us to choose a position.

In psychology, scientists distinguish three different approaches to the personality problem: biological, socializing, biosocial. These approaches view the essence of the concept of personality as an individual property of a person in different ways.

Based on the tasks of our research, we were based on the definition of A. V. Petrovsky, which, in our opinion, reflects not only the essence of the concept of personality, but also the possibilities of changing it.

As a leading characteristic of a person, his orientation is indicated. It is a system of stable motives of a person (values, needs, ideals, outlook, goals). A person's orientation is always socially based and shaped by upbringing.

For us, the specific aspects of the development of the organizer of the person, called abilities, are considered important.

Ability is one of the most general psychological concepts. B. M. Teplov, S. L. Rubinshtein, V. D. Shadrikov, D. N. Zavalishina and others were engaged in the research of this phenomenon in psychology.

B.M. Teplov defined ability as follows: 1) ability - individual psychological characteristics that distinguish a person from other people; 2) specific characteristics related to the successful performance of an activity or several activities; 3) abilities do not refer to the knowledge, skills and abilities created by a person¹.

The effectiveness of abilities is determined by their relationship to a certain type of activity. It is important to show creativity.

S. L. Rubinstein defines creativity as "any creative activity that is new, original, and later enters not only the history of the development of the creator, but also the history of the development of science and art"

"Creativity is the creation of something qualitatively new and characterized by non-repetition, originality and social-historical uniqueness. Creativity is unique to a person, because it always involves the creative activity of the creator - the subject, development occurs in nature, not creativity." It is a person who is creative, genius, talented. We consider this definition to be basic.

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